

Practice abstract #1

Ethnographic research in rural islands to understand social imaginaries: positions regarding climate change

Authors: Florencia Fossa Riglos (Traza)

Editors: Clara Majadas (Traza), Lucía Torres (Traza), Paula Jiménez (Traza), Jesús Febres (R2M Spain), María Ruiz (R2M Spain)

Project coordinator: Jesús Febres (R2M Spain)

Contact person	Florencia Fossa Riglos	florencia.fossa@trazaconsultoria.com		
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More info	https://www.iconic-rural.eu/			

Traza Consultoría
www.trazaconsultoria.com

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Framing and context

Rural islands face interlinked social, economic, and infrastructural challenges that shape how communities perceive and respond to climate change and green transitions.

On **Inis Mór**, the largest Aran Island in Ireland, limited ferry connections constrain access to healthcare, education, and supplies, while tourism pressures, housing shortages, and energy insecurity deepen fragility. In **La**

Graciosa, the smallest Canary Island in Spain, intense seasonal tourism overburdens energy, water, transport, and waste infrastructures, while residents face fluctuating incomes and limited housing. In **Berchidda**, an inland town in Sardinia Island, Italy, depopulation and youth outmigration weaken agriculture and commerce, while seasonal tourism strains mobility, water networks, and waste systems, creating economic and energy vulnerabilities.

These challenges raise a key question: **what is the place of climate change in the everyday lives, practices, and imaginaries of rural island populations?** Understanding this is essential for context-sensitive, climate-just solutions tailored to their social fabric.

Within the framework of the ICONIC project, we implemented an ethnographic research approach to understand local actors' perceptions, social positions and imaginaries regarding climate policies in each island, and to identify pathways for multi-actor governance. Focusing on everyday practices, perceptions (from acceptance to scepticism or denial), and community dynamics, it reveals **how stakeholders interpret climate and environmental challenges, construct meanings around what is considered relevant or irrelevant, attribute responsibilities, and envision potential horizons of action.** It also captures inter-sectoral synergies, frictions, common and specific themes, and the heterogeneous decision-making scales and regulatory frameworks that shape climate responses.

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Objectives

- To **identify challenges**, needs, and opportunities that shape local and public actors' priorities, innovation drivers, and multifaceted problems, providing evidence to guide cross-sectoral and participatory processes.
- To support context-sensitive, climate-just solutions by informing the **co-design of participatory governance** strategies that reflect diverse local perspectives, including non-academic and non-activist groups often distant from formal climate debates.
- Fostering **socially legitimate and sustainable climate action** tailored to each island's unique social fabric.

Methodological approach

We implemented a **mixed-methods approach** combining semi-structured in-depth interviews and socio-demographic profiling for understanding the pilot islands' population, economy, and social structure, across three rural islands. **Actor mapping**, guided by the Quintuple Helix model, used snowball sampling and media/network scans to ensure diverse voices, including critical perspectives. **Interviews** following open-ended, adaptable scripts tailored to organisations, public institutions, and unorganized citizens, were conducted by pilot case leaders in local languages. The materials were analysed through a situated ethnographic lens using thematic coding. Finally, findings were iteratively validated through **collaborative workshops with local coordinators**, enabling context-sensitive interpretation and comparative insights for inclusive, participatory climate governance.

The process was designed to include between **10–15 interviews with diverse civil society stakeholders** at each pilot site, along with **7 interviews with local and regional authorities** including public officers from diverse areas (covering Environment, Economy, Water, Energy, Social Services, Regulatory Affairs, Urban Planning, and associated Citizen Participation bodies).

A **total of 65 semi-structured interviews** were conducted: 24 in La Graciosa, 23 in Inis Mór, and 18 in Berchidda.

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Emerging insights

- **Shared challenges, differentiated priorities:** In La Graciosa and Inis Mór mass tourism drives local pressures, while in Berchidda mobility constraints and limited services are most pressing. Climate change is recognised across all islands, but it is more salient in Berchidda due to tangible agricultural socio-economic impacts.
- **From local issues to climate engagement:** addressing everyday priorities (housing, employment, infrastructure, and services) allows communities to gradually link local concerns to broader climate challenges, supporting inclusive and context-sensitive participation.
- **Grounding governance locally:** Policies anchored in daily realities foster trust and social legitimacy, ignoring these experiences generates fatigue and disengagement.

This knowledge can guide the design of more participatory, context-sensitive methodologies for public innovation that can be adapted to other islands or rural communities. **The insights can inform technological innovations**, such as sustainable renewable energy and water systems, and social innovations through adaptable public innovation methodologies. They are **relevant for multiple actors**: policy-makers designing responsive policies, engineers and planners developing infrastructure aligned with community needs, and local communities engaging in co-creation to ensure legitimate and practical solutions.

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